

Equity Mutual Fund Selection in India- A Decision Tree Approach

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Abstract

The present study related to mutual fund in India is conducted for identifying the factors affecting the mutual fund performance in India which the investors consider for selecting appropriate scheme commonly. The study covers all mutual fund falls under the category of large cap, madcap and small cap and it is found that there is a significant difference in return segmented by that category at 5% level of significance. Different parameters have been studied and found that Expense Ratio, Standard Deviation, Sortino Ratio, Dividend Yield and Sharpe Ratio, Traynor Ratio is statistically different between the selected mutual fund categories(P-value<0.05). Most surprisingly, Other key parameters in literature i.e. Age, Turnover ratio, alpha and size have not shown any significant differences among them. Further, regression tree approach has also been used to explore the key parameters and ratio that may help the investor in selecting mutual fund scheme.

Keywords: Equity, mutual fund selection, decision tree, statistical techniques.

I. Introduction

It can be said that investment in equity dominated mutual funds is just investment in stock market through third parties, the risk components are inherent in it by nature itself. While the basic and prominent objective of investment in mutual funds is to get a trade-off between risk and return, it is necessary to evaluate various mutual fund schemes performance. In portfolio management theories, different ratios and models have been conceptualized and tested under different settings, the most common one are the variations in returns, size of fund, different types of risk return ratios, level of diversification (As proposed by Markowitz to maximize the return for given level of risk) and degree of correlation of portfolio return with market return. As shown in graph and table, as the large cap fund shows comparatively low returns 14.36% as compared to mid cap fund (20.18%) and small cap fund (19.01%) which is attributable to its low volatility, a detailed study of consisting of all types of large cap, mid cap and small cap fund is inevitable to identify the best performance ratios and fund attributes in all. In the present study we have considered all ratios like Sharpe ratio, Traynor ratio, Information ratio, turnover ratio, Sortino ratio, Jensen Alpha as well all fund characteristics like AUM, standard deviation, age of the fund, size of the fund, expenses ratio to explore the predictability of that variables.

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Annual Return				
Type	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Skewness
large cap fund	14.3613	32	2.83227	-1.132
Mid cap fund	20.1852	29	3.60854	1.803
small cap fund	19.0162	29	6.51548	-1.137
Total	17.7378	90	5.17975	-.229

II. Literature Review

Bark (2002) has investigated the relationship between the actively managed portfolio return and fund flow and found that the skills of active manager in a quick portfolio did not guaranteed the Supernormal return that the investor want and form the basis of investment in the active portfolio management and confirms that the past returns cannot be used to predict the future performance of such type of fund. The author has found significant relation between past performance and fund flow but this was found to be due to the market mechanism, not due to the predictive ability of fund manager.

Barbar et.all (2016) has analysed the factor that sophisticated and unsophisticated investors of Mutual fund consider for evaluating equity mutual fund performance. The author has incorporated the netflow of fund as a proxy for investor confidence about the performance and used this as a dependent variable and he found that unsophisticated investors evaluate the fund alpha based on their market adjusted Returns, while sophisticated investor consider all available factors for evaluation. The author demonstrate that the sophisticated investors consider size of the fund value, Momentum, industrial return and sentiment period while unsophisticated investors generally consider the beta factor.

In one of the studies conducted by **Ferreira et.al.(2012)** comprehensive analysis of factors was conducted and in this study cross-country analysis of factors affecting Mutual fund performance was incorporated, It was found that fund size negatively affect the fund performance in US, while in other countries they found that the fund size is Positively associated with the fund performance. The author showed that apart from fund characteristics, country characteristics are also have explanatory power. In predicting, Mitchell, fund performance like financial development in country, stock market, liquidity, strong, legal institutions and rigorous laws. The fund characteristics that they considered was the fund Size ,fund age ,fund expenses, fund flow, past performance and management structure.

A study by **Carhart(1997)** explored the determinants of short-term persistence in equity mutual fund returns and suggested that long term investors should not base their investment decision looking into the performance/ returns in the last year and further the authors found that the expenses ratio, portfolio turnover, transaction cost and load fees have negative impact on mutual fund returns.

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Cook and Hebner (1993) has applied multicriteria approach to mutual fund selection and contended that the investors rank the mutual fund based on various criteria which depends upon their specific set of attributes and preferences rather than a single Jensen's alpha coefficient. The investor can rank the funds based on multiple criteria viz standard deviation of the funds, load fees, the level of diversification, quality of service, and so on that is as per their preferences.

Eshraghi and Taffler(2012) investigate the impact of psychological attributes of fund manager on mutual fund performance and demonstrated that up to greater extent the manager's excessive overconfidence is related with diminished future investment returns in the 12 months following the publication of the annual report while others was able to yield positive average returns after controlling Carhart factors.

III. Research Objectives:

1. To compare the various performance indicators used by investors for selecting equity mutual fund schemes viz large cap, mid cap and small cap mutual fund schemes.
2. To analyze the correlation between various performance indicators used by investors for selecting equity mutual fund schemes.
3. To identify the key performance indicators used by investors for selecting equity mutual fund schemes.

IV. Research Methodology

- i. **Population and Sample:** -For the purpose of this study the mutual fund in India has been considered. To make it comparable, the equity mutual fund under the category of large cap, mid cap and small cap fund has been taken into account with minimum one year of launching of the fund since inception. As the research is based on the secondary data the data relating to all the factors and ratios showing the performance of mutual fund is collected from various websites like moneycontrol mutual fund screener, morning star etc. The data has been collected for 96 mutual fund schemes of large cap, mid cap and small cap categories.
- ii. **Variables-**Annualized Return since inception of the selected schemes is considered as dependent variable classified into four categories viz Low Return (Less than 7%pa), Moderate Return(between 7% to 12%), Good return(between 12% to 15%), High Return(Above 15%pa) for application of CART analysis. The predictor variable included under the study are Age of the fund(in months), Size of the fund(measured through Assets under management-AUM),turnover ratio, expenses ratio, level of diversification(measured through number of stocks),Standard Deviation of returns,Information Ratio, Sortino Ratio, Treynor Ratio,Dividend Yield,Alpha and Treynor Ratio.
- iii. **Statistical Tools-**To compare the various performance indicators ANOVA test is applied and at 5% level of significance, the hypothesis is tested. To analyze the correlation between various performance indicators karlpearson coefficient of correlation is calculated with p-values.as the dependent variable is categorical and other independent variables are continuous on scale, regression tree with CHAID method is applied using SPSS-21 software.

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- iv. **Hypothesis:** The broad null hypothesis is set as “There is no significant difference between predictor variables of large cap, Mid cap and Small Cap funds”.

V. Empirical Results and Analysis

Result-1 ANOVA test

ANOVA						
		<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Turnover Ratio</i>	<i>Between Groups</i>	3.335	2	1.667	2.632	.078
	<i>Within Groups</i>	54.474	86	.633		
	<i>Total</i>	57.809	88			
<i>Annual Return</i>	<i>Between Groups</i>	585.930	2	292.965	14.145	.000
	<i>Within Groups</i>	1801.920	87	20.712		
	<i>Total</i>	2387.850	89			
<i>Age</i>	<i>Between Groups</i>	13824.197	2	6912.099	2.838	.064
	<i>Within Groups</i>	211902.703	87	2435.663		
	<i>Total</i>	225726.900	89			
<i>Size</i>	<i>Between Groups</i>	10.560	2	5.280	2.008	.140
	<i>Within Groups</i>	228.799	87	2.630		
	<i>Total</i>	239.358	89			
<i>Expense Ratio (%)</i>	<i>Between Groups</i>	.716	2	.358	3.512	.034
	<i>Within Groups</i>	8.872	87	.102		
	<i>Total</i>	9.588	89			
<i>Diversification</i>	<i>Between Groups</i>	3.087	2	1.543	5.361	.006
	<i>Within Groups</i>	25.049	87	.288		
	<i>Total</i>	28.136	89			
<i>Standard Return of Past return</i>	<i>Between Groups</i>	428.212	2	214.106	145.279	.000
	<i>Within Groups</i>	128.217	87	1.474		

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	<i>Total</i>	556.429	89			
<i>Information Ratio</i>	<i>Between Groups</i>	.667	2	.334	7.868	.001
	<i>Within Groups</i>	3.689	87	.042		
	<i>Total</i>	4.356	89			
<i>Sortino Ratio</i>	<i>Between Groups</i>	4.814	2	2.407	10.008	.000
	<i>Within Groups</i>	20.923	87	.240		
	<i>Total</i>	25.737	89			
<i>Traynor Ratio</i>	<i>Between Groups</i>	7.039	2	3.519	41.548	.000
	<i>Within Groups</i>	7.369	87	.085		
	<i>Total</i>	14.408	89			
<i>Dividend Yield</i>	<i>Between Groups</i>	3.920	2	1.960	29.290	.000
	<i>Within Groups</i>	5.821	87	.067		
	<i>Total</i>	9.741	89			
<i>Alpha</i>	<i>Between Groups</i>	72.940	2	36.470	2.351	.101
	<i>Within Groups</i>	1349.621	87	15.513		
	<i>Total</i>	1422.561	89			
<i>Sharpe Ratio</i>	<i>Between Groups</i>	1.285	2	.643	12.079	.000
	<i>Within Groups</i>	4.629	87	.053		
	<i>Total</i>	5.914	89			

Interpretation: One way ANOVA test is applied to identify the variables that are significantly different among Large Cap, Mid-Cap, and Small Cap Fund. The test is applied at 5% level of significance and it has been found that Annual Returns, level of diversification, expenses ratio standard deviation, information ratio, sortino ratio, traynor ratio, dividend yield and sharpe ratio has shown the significant difference, however some other key important parameters and ratios like age of the fund, size of the fund, turnover ratio, and Jensen alpha has not shown any significant difference, which is contrary to some research paper in Indian context. one of the most frequently used parameter that is *alpha* and *size* has not shown any significant difference for which deep analysis for identifying the causes is necessary still it indicates that the returns are market dominant and do not exhibit the managerial skill of the fund manager whether it is large cap, madcap or small cap fund to outperform the market.

Result-2 Regression Tree based on Fund Characteristics

Classification Table and correlation

Observed	Predicted				Percent Correct	Correlations		
	LOW RETURN	MODERATE RETURN	GOOD RETURN	HIGH RETURN		DV	Pearson Correlation	Predicted Value
LOW RETURN	3	0	0	0	100.0%	1	.752**	
MODERATE RETURN	0	0	2	0	0.0%			.000
GOOD RETURN	1	0	18	2	85.7%			
HIGH RETURN	1	0	8	55	85.9%			
Overall Percentage	5.6%	0.0%	31.1%	63.3%	84.4%			
						N	90	90

Source: IBM SPSS 21 output

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Interpretation of results: For identifying the key predictor variables belonging to various fund characteristics category, regression tree approach has been adopted, in which the categorized return is taken as dependent variables. The results exhibit that the categories of returns can be split on the basis of size (assets under management) it shows 3 category under Child node one 2 and node 3. Further Split under Child node 2 appears, where the AUM is between ₹553 - ₹3368 Which split on the basis of age (less than 35 month and more than 35 month). If the age of the fund is more than 35 month as shown in node number 5, it can be further split based on expensesRatio. If the fund size is more than ₹ 3358 crore, that is very large fund size, then the type of fund matters to assure the high return. Overall, the model predicts with 84.4% accuracy of prediction as shown in classification table and the correlation between the annual return and predicted value is 0.752, which is significant. This shows the good fit of the model.

Result-3 Regression Tree based on Various Performance Ratio

Classification Table

Observed	Predicted				Percent Correct
	LOW RETURN	MODERATE RETURN	GOOD RETURN	HIGH RETURN	
LOW RETURN	0	0	3	0	0.0%
MODERATE RETURN	0	0	2	0	0.0%
GOOD RETURN	0	0	18	3	85.7%
HIGH RETURN	0	0	6	58	90.6%
Overall Percentage	0.0%	0.0%	32.2%	67.8%	84.4%

Source: IBM SPSS 21 output

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Interpretation of results: For identifying the key predictor ratios belonging to various fund performance categories, regression tree approach has been adopted, in which the categorized return is taken as dependent variables. The results show that the categories of returns can be split based on Sharpe Ratio. If the Sharpe ratio is greater than 0.920 then there is a good probability of high return (More than 15%) however if sharp ratio is between 0.600 to 0.920 then as shown in Node-2, for ensuring high return the Traynor ratio should be used and if it is greater than 0.910 it should be preferred. If sharp ratio is less than 0.600 then the chance of return is between 12% to 15%. Classification table shows 84.4% accuracy in prediction which can be interpreted as a good fit model.

VII. Conclusion

The present study on one hand explores the different mutual fund characteristics that have significant impact upon the performance of the large, mid and small cap funds and on another hand, the study has also explored the fund performance ratios that shows better predictability. The results show that level of diversification, expenses ratio, standard deviation, information ratio, Sortino ratio, Treynor ratio, dividend yield and Sharpe ratio are significantly different in large, mid and small cap fund while some other key important variables and ratios like age of the fund, size of the fund, turnover ratio, and Jensen alpha are not differed significantly. Our decision tree model shows that the first key criteria that differentiate different degrees of return is AUM while age > 35 and expenses ratio < 0.810 also ensure the high return. also, if size of the fund is too large that is to say more than ₹ 3358 crore, than only fund category has exploratory power to differentiate return class. Out of the various ratios only two ratios i.e. Sharpe ratio and Treynor ratio have predictive power. So the study suggest that investors should not make their investment decision based solely on fund alpha, size of fund and age of fund which is most common among investors.

VI. Limitation of the Study

The present study has only consider the large cap, madcap and small cap funds. Also, the investor category based on their preferences and attributes has also been ignored. We also did not conducted the study that categorise sophisticated and unsophisticated investors.

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